

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Gajathar**FIRST NAME:** Ashvena**PROGRAM CODE:** DIPH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: SUMMARY OF COURSEWORK

1. ZOTERO is a referencing tool that allows you to collect, save, and organize your research. Which of the following statements is correct?
 - Saves the PDF only and does not retrieve the metadata.
 - Collect information about primary and secondary sources, such as journal articles, books, interviews, letters, maps, and movies.¹**
 - Zotero only includes the article's title, authors, and journal name for journal articles.
 - The easiest way to add items to Zotero is manually.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, first ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2024), 2.

2. Select the correct Turabian formatting guidelines.
- In the author-date style, in-text citations appear in parentheses, with a reference list listing all your sources at the end.²**
 - Bibliography entries are alphabetized by author's first name.
 - Author-date in-text citations consist of the author's last name, the year of publication, and a page number is irrelevant.
 - Turabian style capitalizes the first word of the title and proper nouns within a title.
 - Turabian Style requires you to use in-text citations, not footnotes.
3. Which sources may not be omitted from the Turabian bibliography?
- brief published items, such as abstracts, pamphlets, reports and reviews of published works or performances
 - newspaper articles
 - blog posts and comments, postings to social media or online forums or mailing lists, and interviews and personal communications.
 - the Bible and other sacred works
 - Selected Bibliography³**
4. What are some of the key components of the Dissertation Concept?
- A brief research proposal of 100 pages

² Kate Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 159.

³ Ibid., 159.

- A complete plan for executing the dissertation.
 - Provides an opportunity for the supervisory committee to review the appropriateness of the research questions based on the student's critical literature review.
 - Describes what might be studied in the proposed dissertation, why it needs to be studied, and how it might be studied.**⁴
5. Quantitative and qualitative researchers acknowledge that the potential for bias exists in research. Which of the following statements is correct when considering the potential for **theory** bias?
- Occurs when personal experiences using interventions in practice leading to perceived effectiveness and ineffectiveness of specific strategies.
 - Need to establish or eliminate one or more public policies.
 - Results from perceived efficacy of specific constructs conceptualising human development, service delivery and personality interventions.**⁵
 - With a variable being examined in the research, either positive or negative, e.g. an outstanding achievement or a serious problem.
6. We review the literature for dissertation research to:
- Understand what is already known about the topic.
 - allows the reader to understand the variables examined in the dissertation.

⁴ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee: University of Florida State, 2017), 2–3.

⁵ Ibid., 9.

- justify the research question examined for the dissertation.
- Know what concepts and theories have been applied to the topic.
- all of the above.**⁶

7. Validity concerns the accumulation of evidence about how an instrument or test measures what it intends to measure. Select the correct statement.

- Helps the reader determine that differences or relationships among variables exist.**⁷
- Like hypotheses that can never be proven true, validity can be established.
- Validity is not a judgment call but is based on factorial empirical measures.
- Unable to determine accurate evidence that exists for discrimination between groups of people.

8. Research implications provide recommendations based on the knowledge gained from the dissertation research to advance future research in the following policies. Select the correct answer.

- Theory development.
- Future research.
- Education policies.
- Public policy.

⁶ Ibid., 31–32.

⁷ Ibid., 40–41.

- All of the above.**⁸
9. When presenting tables or figures, you have several options if you cannot make a table or figure fit on a page. Select the correct option to fit the table in your dissertation best.
- Portrait.
- Landscape with main text included.
- Omit from the dissertation.
- Appendix.**⁹
- Single Page.
10. The WHO style guide on footnotes recommends that footnotes be kept at minimum length and numbers. Which of the following formats is another recommendation for footnotes?
- Place footnotes at the bottom of the page on which footnote references appear.**¹⁰
- Use superscript Calibri numbers to identify footnotes.
- If the same footnote is used several times on the page, you don't have to reference it again.
- Reference marks should be placed before the punctuation.

⁸ Ibid., 60–62.

⁹ Ibid, 382–83.

¹⁰ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, 2nd ed. (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 53.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.